

CLASSIFIERS AND PREPOSITIONAL PHRASES IN ENGLISH

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The purpose of this article is to bring into discussion the structure of classifiers and of prepositional phrases in English, in order to offer a parallel to Japanese similar constructions. As we know, the linguistic system of English employs definite and indefinite articles in order to express definiteness, but classifiers are also present mostly in the form of prepositional phrases. Unlike Japanese, where the nouns are intrinsically non-definite, nouns in English are either definite or indefinite. The only equivalent is in the form of mass nouns, which cannot be differentiated as a whole. For this reason, English makes use of classifiers so that these substances can be differentiated in the form of part of a sequence. However, the structure of classifiers is not the same as in Japanese, since here they are mostly prepositional phrases, while in Japanese they form a closed class of elements.

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14.0. Classifiers in English - A Summarized Review

Although not a classifier language, English exhibits an open class of words that are functionally similar to classifiers: *a HEAD of lettuce, a HERD of cattle, a BOX of candy*. For some words the collocational and lexical features must be represented directly in the lexicon. For example, *pride* would be listed as the collective classifier for *lion*. Classifiers are not semantically rigid, however, as it is evident in the extended listings from lexicons (*a HERD of linguists* and *a FLOCK of linguists*). In many cases, the lexicon fully integrates the semantic content of the classifier in the lexical employment of the word per-se. Novel occurrences of words in classifier NP constructions (*a HOARD of statues*) involve pragmatic interpretation criteria which are triggered by the ordinary specification of conventional classifiers in lexicons. The appendix on the syntax of classifiers in English emphasizes that all the syntactic tests which purport to make measure phrases distinguishable in partitives, pseudo-partitives, and complement PPs show the employment of classifiers to be syntactically determined phenomena, and not hazardous theories.

Among the constructions in English which have the surface linear structure ((Del) N of (Del) N] there is a significant subgroup, that of classifiers made up of partitives, pseudo-partitives, and measure phrases. We can exemplify these groups in terms of syntagms that abide by the following structures:

- 471. a bunch of carrots
- hundreds of animals
- two pounds of flour
- a number of individuals
- a herd of bovines

English is considered to be a classifierless language, since classifier languages, as described by Greenberg (1972), Allan (1977), Denny (1976,1979), Adams and Conklin (1973), and others, have a closed small and paradigmatically contrasting data of lexemes, which are mandatory, at least in some contexts. In English, classifiers are often employed when individuating masses, their occurrence is not always obligatory. Thus it is acceptable:

- 472. Waiter, bring me wine, please.

Moreover, mass nouns are freely used as count nouns, and any implicit classifier would be determined by the pragmatics of the situation.

- 473 a. Waiter, can you please bring 2 coffees (cups of coffee)
- b. Five coffees are evidently high in caffeine. (kinds of coffee)
- c. Can you bring down the coffees up there? (cans, packages of coffee)

Since English does not have a closed set of classifiers, (but instead an open and productive class), we must look at the rather complex interaction of syntactic, semantic, collocational, and pragmatic factors that apply to words which could be used as classifiers, both as conventional classifiers and as novel ones. The syntactic form of classifier expressions in English is:

(Det) N,(of (Det) NA

In most cases *of* cannot be replaced by another preposition, nor can it be paraphrased as a compound which reverses the order of the two nouns. *A cup of jewels*, or, in other words, *'the amount of jewels that a cup maintains*, its not semantically identical with syntagms like *cup with jewels. cup for jewels, or jewel cup*. There are instances where the prepositional phrase can be postposed or preposed, as in (474a,b):

- 474. a. A dozen was wasted of those paintballs by professional shooters.
- b. Of the carrots that I was talking about, two sacks were used.

There are a number of interesting syntactic problems involved in classifier expressions, such as which noun is the head, whether *of* should be generated in deep structure, whether *of* and the following noun phrase constitute a prepositional phrase, and whether different deep structures distinguish *a bunch of the carrots* from *a bunch of carrots*. The latter is interesting to analyze because it would show whether classifiers in English contribute to the definite interpretation of Noun Phrases or not, but this issue can simply be brought into discussion by emphasizing that they always determine pluralized nouns which are argued to be definite by most researchers. From these examples another important observation is that the classifier, a noun itself,

can bear a definite or an indefinite article, so it means that at the syntactic structure, it behaves like a common noun, unlike Japanese, where they form a closed class of elements.

Allan's taxonomy of classifiers for English categorizes the classifiers according to a number of criteria, but their number is way smaller than in Asian languages and this illustrates the range of constructions they express (Allan, 1977). The author provides seven categories for English classifiers, but it is neither disjoint or exhaustive.

475.

(a) Unit counters: *a part of equipment, three heads of bovines.*

(b) Fractional classifiers: *2 quarters of the pie.*

(c) Number set classifiers: *many thousands of men, dozens of cats.*

(d) Collective classifiers: *Three clumps of herbs, a herd of wolves.*

(e) Varietal classifiers: *Two species of cauliflower, all types of anemones.*

(f) Measure classifiers: *Two pounds of potatoes, a box of candy, one liter of juice*

(g) Arrangement classifiers: *Two columns of flowers, four stacks of magazines.*

There is another group of classifiers, which some authors bring into discussion, although their existence *per se* is a matter of discussion. These include expressions like *a monster of a man, a slip of a woman, and a horror of a life*. They are typically named 'metaphorical comparison' classifiers, since their interpretation seems to involve a comparison between the two nouns, and the innovative characteristic is the noun interpreted metaphorically. In terms of their properties, classifiers are usually analyzed by means of binary features. I give a few examples below, taken from Lehrer (1985)

476.

a. Kind : + N + count

varietal classifier of [N PI • 'a class of things' •

plural refers to number agreement between N, and N,

a kind of book; several kinds of books

b. Crowd : +N , +count + Verb Classifier use follows from the meaning.

'large number of people gathered together'

c. List : +N

an arrangement of written or printed items, often of a specified + count category'

Some classifiers are deeply cojoined with particular nouns, and conversely, certain nouns are empirically determined by a number of classifiers. Venerly terms especially fall into this group. *'In English there is a unique association between the collective classifier pride and the noun lions and similarly between gaggle and geese'* (Allan, 1977). A similar situation arises in Japanese, where classifiers are closed classes of elements that are grouped on several criteria and are highly specific regarding the category of noun they determine. In this respect they depart from their English counterpart, which are much little in number and which do not function as mandatory constituents of Number:

477. a herd of deer, cattle, horses, goats

a pack of hyenas, dogs, tigers, coyotes

a flock of geese, sheep, a pride of lions

a school of dolphins, a pod of seals

It has often been underlined that classifier languages like Japanese or Chinese, often employ *shape* as a foundation for categorizing (Denny: 1976,1979), Adams and Concklin (1973), and that this criterion represents a striking peculiarity of phenomena which children make use of when acquiring their language. Evidently enough, *bottom* and *shaft* have a semantic clue of shape in their structure. This pattern is repeated by a large number of other English classifiers. We can bring into discussion unit classifiers: *cube, pinch, ball, slice, loaf, sheet*, while arrangement classifiers follow: *field, column, row, heap, stack*. These classifiers are characterized by a relatively free distribution and can determine mostly nouns which adopt a certain shape: *rod, wad, thread, dough, ball, sheet, yarn* of etc.

478. *To season the soup correctly, add a pinch of pepper, a grind of salt, a dash of bay, a sprinkle of lovage, a shake of mint, and a toss of finely scraped onions.*

One important argument comes from the conventionalized classifier *slice*, which has become a noun through the process of categorization. It is a classifier of shape and shows that there is a determined process that permeates the phenomena of classifiers in English, since it is originally a verb. Lexically, we employ it to denote a sorce of a three-dimensional substance divided so that its description relatively includes the adjectives *thin, broad, and flat* and it usually results from the process of cutting. The process is productive with deverbal classifiers, allowing novel combinations in original NPs:

14.1. Conclusions of This Section

Classifiers are a unique class of elements that behave separately in Japanese than in English and their structure must be understood in the latter so as to underline their peculiarity and the role they play in Japanese. For this reason, the previous section works as a foil towards the chapter that analyzes classifiers as means of rendering the definite interpretation of Noun Phrases grammatical in Japanese. Had this not been our goal, the present section would bear a little interest, because classifiers in English hold nothing special in comparison to other common nouns and they do not contribute to the semantic or syntactic structure of these nouns with much new information.

One important consequence of studying classifiers in English is the observation that they are lexical items, unlike Japanese, where they are analyzed as functional lexemes. They are common nouns that can be both definite or indefinite and always determine a pluralized Noun Phrase to which they attach as a Quantifier Phrase. Moreover, they are syntactically analyzed in terms of their nominality and countability, even though, as examples presented above would suggest, they could also accept the binary dichotomy definite/indefinite. One similarity with Asian languages is that in English classifiers are roughly classified in terms of their shape or as deverbal nominals, which follows the trend in Chinese or Japanese, for example, where they usually

serve as criteria for the classification of nouns in different classes of elements based on a peculiar characteristic like shape, form, dimension, type of animals, instruments etc. However, their number is much smaller so one cannot conclude that they serve the same purpose like their counterpart do.

Classifiers in English are employed to quantify mass or collective nouns, or bare plurals that cannot be singularized by suffixation or by any syntactic means available in English and they form a Noun Phrase together with the noun they determine, maintaining their status as Quantifier Phrases. In order to emphasize that the employment of classifiers in English is not hazardous, we also brought into discussion the Prepositional Phrase Extraposition to underline there are syntactic phenomena at stake that influence their structure and this could be seen in the examples where syntactic diagrams were provided before, but there are yet other

tests like number agreement between the subject head noun and the finite verb, tag questions, preposition stranding etc. they do not contribute at all to the definite interpretation of the noun.

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